

READEUNOIA: THE DEVELOPED COMPANION WORKBOOK INTEGRATING UMBRELLA PROJECT INTO SCHOLASTIC READING PROGRAM FOR GRADE 7 LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

The primary objective of this study was to develop and validate a companion workbook that integrated the social-emotional skills from the Umbrella Project into the reading instruction of Scholastic Reading Program to enhance Grade 7 learners' reading comprehension levels at Asian Computer College, Inc. This study followed the design and development research method. Using purposeful sampling method, this study involved 30 Grade 7 learners and validators consisted of 15 Scholastic Reading Program and Umbrella Project teacher-implementers. Using an adapted four-point Likert scale, mean, frequency, percentage, and t-test, findings revealed that the companion workbook's validity, based on the program teacher-implementers' evaluation of its objectives (3.32), directions (3.53), topics (3.58), and practical exercises (3.57), were all interpreted as highly valid. Similarly, the level of acceptability of the developed companion workbook was all interpreted as highly acceptable based on the assessment of the aforementioned implementers in terms of clarity (3.63), usefulness (3.65), presentation (3.63), and suitability (3.56). The comparison between pretest and posttest results highlighted a significant improvement in the learners' academic performance level. It can be concluded that the developed companion workbook for Grade 7 reading instruction evidently increased the respondents' reading comprehension level based on the difference in their performance in the pretest and posttest.

Keywords: *developed material, reading comprehension, reading skills, social-emotional learning skills, companion workbook*

INTRODUCTION

Improving literacy quality has long been a central concern in education, yet reading comprehension remains a persistent global challenge. UNICEF (2022) reported that only one-third of 10-year-old children worldwide could read and understand a simple story, with 64% failing to meet basic comprehension standards, a sharp increase from 52% before the pandemic. Similarly, the National Assessment of Educational Progress revealed declining reading scores among U.S. fourth and eighth graders, despite decades of literacy programs (NAEP, 2022).

In the Philippines, the situation is even more critical. Pre-pandemic data showed that 70% of 10-year-old Filipino children struggled with basic text comprehension, a figure that rose to 90% during COVID-19 disruptions. Filipino students' reading performance ranked significantly below international averages which underscored systematic literacy challenges.

Schools have attempted to address these issues through structured programs such as the Scholastic Reading Program, which includes activities like read-alouds, literacy weeks, and guided reading interventions. Scholastic Inc., recognized globally as a leader in literacy publishing, developed the Scholastic Reading Inventory (SRI) to assess comprehension levels using the Lexile Framework. Several research had demonstrated its effectiveness: Daboul (2020) found that Below Basic Readers engaged in Scholastic Reading Program interventions exhibited three times greater growth than non-participants. Oposa et al. (2025) proved a significant gain among Grade 1 students using Scholastic Literacy Pro. Silva et al. (2023) highlighted the effectiveness of read-aloud sessions. In order to maximize the literacy effects of the program, Garing et al. (2020) noted that teacher self-efficacy had a strong influence to student motivation. And Maleon (2022) further identified home and school factors as determinants of reading comprehension (Lexile) scores.

Despite these efforts, challenges in reading remain. At Asian Computer College, Inc. after eight years of implementing the Scholastic Reading Program, 72% of students were still recommended for reading intervention. Students' testimonies revealed that emotional barriers like fear, anxiety, low confidence, and shame were as detrimental as cognitive deficits in vocabulary or fluency. This shows a research gap: literacy programs often emphasized technical skills but neglect the social-emotional dimensions of learning.

Social-emotional learning (SEL) programs have consistently shown positive impacts on student achievement and well-being. Savitz and Ippolito (2023) emphasized resilience, empathy, and motivation as key SEL outcomes. The Umbrella Project, developed by Dr. Jen Forristal, equips students with coping skills through inquiry-driven lessons. Hurtubise et al. (2022) confirmed its effectiveness in improving SEL competencies, while Ferrer (2023) and Tabalanza et al. (2022) highlighted its role in fostering holistic growth and academic success.

That being so, to improve the reading comprehension level of the students, reading should be integrated with social-emotional learning skills incorporated in a learning material became the rationale of this study. This particular initiative was supported by published literature. Quiamno (2021) recommended from his paper that it may be

interesting to integrate social-emotional learning skills into an existing school curriculum and programs. When social-emotional learning is integrated into another program or an instruction, positive results in learning have been observed. In the findings of Laufenberg (2020), the reading proficiency level of the students had improved after implementing literacy lessons integrated with social-emotional skills.

Being guided by the recommendations from the existing body of studies, this paved the way for the researcher to develop a companion workbook that aims to integrate social-emotional learning skills to the reading instruction to enhance the reading comprehension level of the learners. Hence, READEunoia: An SEL-infused Literacy Companion Workbook was proposed. This was a holistic literacy material that was used to enhance the reading comprehension level of the learners, bridging the missing gaps in the teaching-learning of reading instruction in the school.

Research Objectives

The major goal of this research, *READEUNOIA: The Developed Companion Workbook Integrating Umbrella Project into Scholastic Reading Program for Grade 7 Learners*, was to enhance the reading comprehension level of the respondents through integrating the Umbrella Project skills into the Scholastic Reading Program using the developed companion workbook.

Specifically, this research sought the following research objectives:

1. Design a companion workbook material that integrates Umbrella Project into the Scholastic Reading Program in Grade 7 reading instruction.
2. Establish the content validity and acceptability of the designed companion workbook material in Grade 7 reading instruction; and,
3. Determine the pretest and posttest results of the Grade 7 students' reading comprehension level before and after implementing the developed and validated companion workbook.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research with the pivotal goal of developing companion workbook that integrated the Umbrella Project's social-emotional skills into the Scholastic Reading Program used and employed the design and developmental research method.

Design and Developmental Research Method, as mentioned by Richey and Klein (as cited in Unico, 2022) was a systematic study of the processes of designing, creating, developing, and evaluating educational tools, materials, or improved models. This particular research design involved a more structured process of designing, developing, and evaluating instructional tools.

Using the Design and Development Research method, a companion workbook material in Grade 7 reading instruction was to develop and be used as a supplementary material that accompanied the existing programs. This developed workbook contained exercises, activities, and reading materials related to the main content.

The design and developmental research method was employed because of the three major reasons; (1.) A companion workbook was intended to provide learners with the opportunity to experience meaningful reading by incorporating social-emotional learning skills. This particular reason was grounded in the belief that cognitive, cultural, and social-emotional capabilities should be integrated moving beyond the idea of mere decoding of written words, (2). It was observed that the two programs independently interplayed their objectives independently. The two programs involved in the study are partially implemented, with partial implementation as the social-emotional skill program existed as “siloed”, and (3). the gap between theory and practice was intended to be bridged through the companion workbook ensuring that the learning approach was not only theoretically sound but also applicable to learning process and reading instruction.

Research Locale

Asian Computer College, Inc. (ACC) was selected as the research locale for this study as the school adopted two learning programs that were important to the present research study.

Asian Computer College adopted the Scholastic Reading Program on June 2017 pursuing the idea of making the learners learn reading and love reading. For the past 8 years, the implementation of the program has been observed overall good, although there were still challenges had been encountered.

This school was the first school that adopted the Umbrella Project in all Southeast Asian countries which the primary aim was to enhance the well-being of the students. For four (4) years, the school had been providing wellness activities. One notable activity in the school is its morning program session, the Strong Start Session Program, which enabled the social-emotional implementers to explicitly teach the students mental health strategies and target social-emotional learning skills. The objective of this program was to bring Umbrella Project into the daily morning routine which was believed to help students start their day “strong”.

Population and Sampling

The study employed purposive sampling, a technique described by Campbell et al. (2020), which involved intentionally selecting respondents based on specific characteristics relevant to the research objectives. Respondents were intentionally the chosen based on the results of an online research-based reading test, the Scholastic Reading Inventory (SRI). The Grade 7 class, diagnosed by the Scholastic Reading Inventory as Below Basic Reader, was sought to be the respondents of the study. As mentioned, the respondents’ initial reading level to group them which adhered to the

theory of zone of proximal development. This particular selected section of Grade 7 was composed of a mixture of below basic readers (18 students), basic readers (6 students), and proficient readers (6 students) which was considered perfectly fitted in the objectives of this research.

Table 1

Grade 7 Reading Comprehension Level using the Scholastic Reading Inventory

Respondents	Lexile Level	Reading Comprehension Level
Student 1	1025L	Proficient Reader
Student 2	663L	Below Basic Reader
Student 3	847L	Basic Reader
Student 4	825L	Basic Reader
Student 5	179L	Below Basic Reader
Student 6	1058L	Proficient Reader
Student 7	1031L	Proficient Reader
Student 8	239L	Below Basic Reader
Student 9	703L	Below Basic Reader
Student 10	935L	Basic Reader
Student 11	865L	Basic Reader
Student 12	657L	Below Basic Reader
Student 13	221L	Below Basic Reader
Student 14	387L	Below Basic Reader
Student 15	986L	Proficient Reader
Student 16	332L	Below Basic Reader
Student 17	391L	Below Basic Reader
Student 18	927L	Basic Reader
Student 19	641L	Below Basic Reader
Student 20	676L	Below Basic Reader
Student 21	414L	Below Basic Reader
Student 22	568L	Below Basic Reader
Student 23	706L	Below Basic Reader
Student 24	870L	Basic Reader
Student 25	533L	Below Basic Reader
Student 26	1017L	Proficient Reader
Student 27	557L	Below Basic Reader
Student 28	317L	Below Basic Reader
Student 29	1002L	Proficient Reader
Student 30	340L	Below Basic Reader
Average Lexile Level	663L	BELOW BASIC READER

Table 1 presented the initial reading comprehension level and average level of the target respondents, and this was used for selecting reading texts. Through the help of the fictional texts, guided group discussions, and activities that were centered on the social-emotional learning themes, respondents were expected to reflect their own emotions and

background experiences which deeper understanding and comprehension of the text which expected to become possible.

Respondents of the Study

The focus of this study was the Grade 7 students who were diagnosed by the Scholastic Reading Inventory (SRI) as Below Basic Readers. This research considered the respondents having the Lexile ranges from Beginning Readers (BR) to 765L as the class’s average reading level.

Table 2

Grade 7 Lexile Ranges according to SRI Lexile Framework

Reading Comprehension Level (SRI Format)	Lexile Ranges
Below Basic Reader	BR to 765L
Basic Reader	770L to 965L
Proficient Reader	970L to 1120L
Advanced Reader	1125L Above

Since the average reading comprehension level of the respondents was 663L, as mentioned in Table 1, the class proficiency level was **BELOW BASIC READER**. Table 2 presented the Lexile ranges for Grade 7 students, according to the Lexile Framework. To manage the respondents, they were grouped into 5 groups adhering to the Zone of Proximal Development Theory and the Guided Reading Approach.

Table 3

Grade 7 Groupings According to Lexile using the Guided Reading Approach

Reading Group A	Reading Group B	Reading Group C	Reading Group D	Reading Group E
1058L	1031L	1025L	1017L	1002L
706L	703L	825L	847L	986L
663L	657L	676L	641L	935L
387L	533L	568L	557L	927L
340L	317L	414L	391L	870L
239L	221L	179L	332L	865L

It was noted that for each group, a more knowledgeable one was selected as the reading group’s leader, who are called as the groups’ more proficient readers. This guide was also used in the careful selection of stories which, according to the theory, respondents were supposed to be “scaffolded” so that their reading comprehension will

be developed. On the other hand, Table 3 revealed the summary of the target respondents who have been utilized in the study. For the teacher-validators, purposive sampling was also used. Only those teachers who were implementers of Scholastic Reading Program and Umbrella Project were considered as validators.

This research chose these teacher-validators because of their specialized experience, expertise, and exposure of the two programs. As implementers of both learning programs, they have the firsthand knowledge of the programs' objectives, content, student context, and strategies. It was believed that focusing on those teacher-validators directly involved in the implementation of these target research variables, the study's output was ensured that the feedback and evaluation would be both informed and practical which may strengthen the credibility and usefulness of the developed companion workbook.

Table 4

Total Population of Grade 7 Students and Expert-Validators Employed in the Research

No.	School	Grade 7 Students	Scholastic Reading Program and Umbrella Project Implementers
1	Asian Computer College - MAIN Active	30	8
2	Community Contributors Institute	0	7
TOTAL		30	15

Research Instrument

The present study utilized two (2) research instruments, a researcher-made pretest and posttest, and an expert validation tool. The first instrument was developed to evaluate the reading comprehension level of the respondents. The second instrument was adopted from the study of Unico (2022), *The Developed Contextualized Instructional Material in Grade 9 Economics*.

The pretest and posttest were developed and patterned according to the principles of the main theory of this study - the Construction-Integration theory of Reading Comprehension of Walter Kintsch and David Welsch. This believes that comprehension will only occur if readers integrate their background knowledge into the newly presented knowledge.

Lastly, the pretest and posttest were administered to the respondents to determine the significant difference between the pretest and posttest. The results of the performance were interpreted using the levels of proficiency.

Levels of Proficiency

Level	Percentage
Outstanding	90-100
Very Satisfactory	85-89
Satisfactory	80-84
Fairly Satisfactory	75-79
Did Not Meet Expectations	74 - Below

Source: DepEd Order No. 8, S. 2015 (Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program)

Validation of the Instrument

The tool for expert validation was used for this study was originally came from the research study of Unico (2022). This expert validation tool underwent Cronbach's Alpha for reliability with a coefficient of 0.851 for content validity and 0.846. There were two parts of the validation; Part 1 assessed the validity of the companion workbook for Grade 7 with an emphasis on objectives, topics, direction, and practical exercise. On the other hand, Part 2 evaluated the acceptability of the companion workbook based on clarity, usefulness, presentation, and suitability. To interpret the assessment of the validators, the four-point Likert scale was applied and interpreted as follows:

Four-point Likert Scale

Scale	Range	Level of Validity	Level of Acceptability
4	3.25 – 4.00	Highly Valid (HV)	Highly Acceptable (HA)
3	2.50 – 3.24	Valid (V)	Acceptable (A)
2	1.75 – 2.49	Slightly Valid (SV)	Slightly Acceptable (SA)
1	1.00 – 1.74	Not Valid (NV)	Not Acceptable (NA)

Data Gathering Procedure

Through the help of the ADDIE model, this research followed the procedure in data gathering:

In the initial phase of the research, the focus was on assessing the initial reading comprehension levels of the junior high school students using the school's adopted computer-based reading comprehension test which was the Scholastic Reading Inventory (SRI). After determining the level of reading comprehension among the junior high school department, it was revealed that in Grade 7 the highest number of below basic readers were attending, as shown in table 1.

After gathering all Grade 7 students' Lexile level, it was averaged. Through this process, this research was able to identify reading materials which were appropriate to the respondents' average reading comprehension level. Following the design and development phases, this research aligned the learning competencies from the two programs, the Scholastic Reading Program and the Umbrella Project. After designing the companion workbook, experts were sought to validate the material before the actual implementation.

When the experts validated the companion workbook and adhered to their recommendations, a letter was given to the school president requesting the administration of the study. The pretest and posttest of the study for the group of thirty (30) student-respondents were administered. Between the pretest and the posttest, the validated companion workbook was used for five (5) weeks.

To ensure accurate statistical treatment, a statistician was sought. The analysis was conducted to identify any significant difference between the pretest and posttest of reading comprehension and with necessary revisions made to the workbook based on findings before reporting progress to the school administration.

Treatment of Quantitative Data

The study utilized various statistical treatments with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) such as:

1. The level of validity and acceptability of the Grade 7 Companion Workbook was assessed using measures such as mean, frequency, percentage, and Likert scale.
2. The performance of Grade 7 students in the pretest and posttest results was compared using the t-test to determine if there is a significant difference.
3. The standard deviation (SD) was calculated to measure the dispersion of scores in the content validity and acceptability levels.

RESULTS

This presents the collected data accompanied with a thorough, comprehensive analysis, and a meaningful interpretation towards the integration of social-emotional skills into reading instruction using the developed companion workbook which was designed and used to improve the reading comprehension of the target respondents. Moreover, this study also aimed to detail and evaluate the level of validity and acceptability of the developed companion workbook in Grade 7 reading instruction.

Research Objective 1: Design a Companion Workbook Material that integrates Umbrella Project into the Scholastic Reading Program in Grade 7 Reading Instruction.

The developed companion workbook for Grade 7 learners was designed to combine the capacities of the two learning programs of the school which were the Scholastic Reading Program and the Umbrella Project. The companion workbook was developed according to the reading skills and social-emotional topics included in the programs. Along the theories, this research used also 3 reading approaches; the pre-during-post reading, guided reading, and contextual reading approaches to help the respondents learn reading as guided by the theoretical underpinnings of this study.

Research Objective 2: Establish the content validity and acceptability of the designed Companion Workbook Material in Grade 7 Reading Instruction.

Table 5

Content Validity Level of Companion Workbook Integrating Umbrella Project into Scholastic Reading Program for Grade 7 Learners in terms of Objectives

Indicators	\bar{x}	VI
1. Relevant to the Scholastic topics in Grade 7.	2.93	V
2. Specific and clearly stated.	3.20	V
3. Measurable, attainable, and result-oriented.	3.73	HV
4. Well-planned, formulated, and organized.	3.13	V
5. Time-bound.	3.60	HV
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.32	HV
Standard Deviation	0.18	

Table 6**Content Validity Level of Companion Workbook Integrating Umbrella Project into Scholastic Reading Program for Grade 7 Learners in terms of Directions**

Indicators	\bar{x}	VI
1. Simple and clear.	3.60	HV
2. Easy to follow.	3.33	HV
3. Properly sequenced.	3.33	HV
4. Can be done independently.	3.87	HV
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.53	HV
Standard Deviation	0.23	

Table 7**Content Validity Level of Companion Workbook Integrating Umbrella Project into Scholastic Reading Program for Grade 7 Learners in terms of Topics**

Indicators	\bar{x}	VI
1. Aligned with the Scholastic Reading Skills and Umbrella Project skills.	3.73	HV
2. Logically presented.	3.33	HV
3. Address the learner's needs.	3.27	HV
4. With background concepts.	4.00	HV
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.58	HV
Standard Deviation	0.28	

Table 8**Content Validity Level of Companion Workbook Integrating Umbrella Project into Scholastic Reading Program for Grade 7 Learners in terms of Practical Exercises**

Indicators	\bar{x}	VI
1. Relevant to the objectives.	3.73	HV
2. Appropriate to learners' abilities.	3.47	HV
3. Adequate to the learners' comprehension and reading level.	3.47	HV
4. Sufficient enough to determine the mastery level of learners.	3.47	HV
5. Stimulate higher-order thinking skills.	3.73	HV
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.57	HV
Standard Deviation	0.27	

Table 9**Level of Acceptability of Companion Workbook Integrating Umbrella Project into Scholastic Reading Program for Grade 7 Learners in terms of Clarity**

Indicators	\bar{x}	VI
1. Information is clear and simple.	3.93	HA
2. Language used is clear and easy to understand.	3.60	HA
3. The concepts for each activity are re-arranged logically and ensure that there is no duplication.	3.53	HA
4. Information suits learners' interest.	3.47	HA
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.63	HA
Standard Deviation	0.40	

Table 10**Level of Acceptability of Companion Workbook Integrating Umbrella Project into Scholastic Reading Program for Grade 7 Learners in terms of Usefulness**

Indicators	\bar{x}	VI
1. The material prepares the learners to think logically and critically.	3.67	HA
2. The concepts in the material are simple and comprehensible.	3.73	HA
3. The material helps the students master the topics at their own pace.	3.60	HA
4. The material provides an opportunity for development.	3.60	HA
5. The learning contents provide adequate information on the topics presented.	3.60	
6. The material motivates learners to become actively involved in the learning activities.	3.73	HA
7. The material stimulates the learners to intellectual activities which help them master the Scholastic reading skills.	3.47	HA
8. The activities seek to relate new concepts from previous learning.	3.80	HA
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.65	HA
Standard Deviation	0.24	

Table 11

Level of Acceptability of Companion Workbook Integrating Umbrella Project into Scholastic Reading Program for Grade 7 Learners in terms of Presentation

Indicators	\bar{x}	VI
1. Topics are presented in logical and sequential order.	3.80	HA
2. The direction is concise, readable, and easy to follow.	3.47	HA
3. The topics fit the learners' needs.	3.53	HA
4. The presentation of each lesson is attractive and interesting.	3.73	HA
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.63	HA
Standard Deviation	0.42	

Table 12

Level of Acceptability of Companion Workbook Integrating Umbrella Project into Scholastic Reading Program for Grade 7 Learners in terms of Suitability

Indicators	\bar{x}	VI
1. Activities consider the varying attitudes and capabilities of the learner.	3.80	HA
2. Activities are appropriate to the subject matter.	3.67	HA
3. Activities are relevant, interesting, and self-motivating to the learners.	3.53	HA
4. Enrichment activities cater to the different learning needs of learners.	3.60	HA
5. Language of the program is within the vocabulary range of the learners.	3.20	A
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.56	HA
Standard Deviation	0.32	

Research Objective 3: Determine the pretest and posttest results of the Grade 7 students' reading comprehension level before and after implementing the developed and validated Companion Workbook.

Table 13

Significant Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Grade 7 Learners

Test	Paired Differences				Remarks	Decision
	Mean	SD	T	P value		

Pretest and Posttest	-7.53	7.06	-5.844	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
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Table 14
Pretest Score of the Grade 7 Students

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	18	60.00
Very Satisfactory	5	16.67
Satisfactory	5	16.67
Fairly Satisfactory	1	3.33
Did Not Meet Expectations	1	3.33
Total	30	100.00
Average	88.40	Very Satisfactory

Table 15
Posttest Score of the Grade 7 Students

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	30	100
Very Satisfactory	0	0
Satisfactory	0	0
Fairly Satisfactory	0	0
Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0
Total	30	100.00
Average	95.93	Outstanding

DISCUSSION

Research Objective 2: Establish the content validity and acceptability of the designed Companion Workbook Material in Grade 7 Reading Instruction.

Objectives got **Highly Valid** (3.32). The indicator “Measurable, attainable, and result-oriented” had the highest mean of 3.73 while the indicator “Relevant to the Scholastic topics in Grade 7” had the lowest mean of 2.93 which was **Valid**. It contained a standard deviation of 0.18 which represented homogeneity of the responses.

This means that the objectives of the companion workbook are aligned with the objectives set by the Scholastic Reading Program and Umbrella Project. The

abovementioned result clearly implies that the developed companion workbook's learning objectives were measurable, attainable, and result-oriented.

The objectives of the companion workbook are assessed as **highly valid** because they are clearly structured, practical, and aligned with the Scholastic Reading Program and Umbrella Project. The objectives included in the developed material emphasized measurable and attainable learning outcomes which make it easier for both teachers and students to track progress and see real growth. Through integrating the social-emotional learning skills within the reading instruction, this companion workbook not only supported academic achievement but also nurtured life skills that makes the reading experience of the students to be more meaningful. The standard deviation further supports this results as this indicates a high level of agreement among the interraters which means that the assessment of the objectives is consistently observed. This confirms the homogeneity of responses, thereby reinforcing the reliability and validity of the results.

The idea of measurable, attainable, and result-oriented learning objectives was reflected to some existing studies. According to Utami et al. (2020), the utilization of workbooks to students was continuously providing positive benefits to students' learning outcomes by promoting active learning, enabling the students to independently navigate the material. This aligned to creating measurable, attainable, and results-oriented learning objectives since it emphasized practical use of the content which made the students feel empowered and motivated to achieve the provided reading activities. Through measurable, attainable, and result-oriented learning objectives, the students were to better understand expectations and monitor their own progress which strengthened their reading proficiency.

Directions got **Highly Valid** (3.53). The indicator "Can be done independently" had the highest mean of 3.87 while the indicators "Easy to follow" and "Properly sequenced" have the same lowest mean of 3.33 which were interpreted still as **Highly Valid**. A standard deviation of 0.23 was recorded which reflected low variation in the evaluators' responses.

This implies that the companion workbook's directions are effectively designed in a way that matched the students' current reading abilities while also allowing them to gradually improve without needing constant support. The result above clearly reflects that the workbook provides clear instructions, appropriate scaffolding, and manageable reading tasks which makes it easier for students to engage with the material on their own. The standard deviation indicates low variability in the ratings which implies that the evaluators are generally consistent in their assessments of the directions. This also reinforces that the appropriateness of the directions is observed in the developed companion workbook.

Tolentino et al. (2023), asserted that the role of instructional materials such as booklets should be designed to enable the learners to study by themselves. The research explained that when it comes to providing information in a contemporary educational setting where various learning modalities are simply and every day employed, learning resources were expected to promote independent and individualized learning.

Topics got **Highly Valid** (3.58). The indicator “With background concepts” had the highest mean of 4.00 while the indicator “Address the learner’s needs” had the same lowest mean of 3.27 which was interpreted still as **Highly Valid**. A standard deviation of 0.28 highlighted a moderate variation in the evaluators' responses.

The results above clearly demonstrates that the companion workbook provides students with the necessary foundational knowledge to better understand and engage with the lessons. The topics which are included in the workbook ensures that students are not simply memorizing or completing tasks, but are developing a deeper comprehension of the material. This approach supports reading proficiency by helping the students to connect new ideas to prior knowledge, making reading activities more meaningful and manageable.

This also shows that the topics are thoughtfully organized to build understanding progressively. This is true to the concept of localized materials where students’ background information and experience are incorporated that can help to promote understanding. The standard deviation shows most of the interraters shared similar judgements with a few slightly different views which possibly due to personal teaching contents or interpretation of local relevance.

According to Mayos et al. (2023), the use of localized learning materials is very uniquely effective in integrating students’ culture and local knowledge which can promote an impactful and meaningful educational exercise. Their findings revealed that a localized curriculum helped students better understand texts and facilitated quicker connections between the new information presented by teachers and their existing knowledge frameworks.

Practical Exercises got **Highly Valid** (3.57). The indicators “Relevant to the objectives” and “Stimulate higher-order thinking skills” have the highest mean of 3.73 while the indicators “Appropriate to learners’ abilities, Adequate to the learners’ comprehension and reading level, and Sufficient enough to determine the mastery level of Learners” have the same lowest mean of 3.47 which was interpreted still as **Highly Valid**. The standard deviation of 0.27 denoted a low variation in the evaluators' responses.

It can be concluded that the companion workbook’s practical activities are closely aligned with the intended learning objectives while also challenging students to think critically and deeply about the reading material. The activities in the companion workbook demonstrate a strong connection to the objectives that allows students to recognize the purpose of each task and engage in more focused and meaningful learning.

Furthermore, the companion workbook promotes higher-order thinking skills by encouraging students to analyze, evaluate, and comprehend which pushes the students to move beyond simple recall. The standard deviation indicates a low variation in how the raters assessed the practical exercises. It is because while the majority of the interraters agree that the practical exercises are well-aligned with the objectives, a few interraters might have had slightly different views on the degree to which the practical exercises challenge students. Nevertheless, the low standard deviation shows that the evaluation

is still largely consistent in reinforcing the strength of the companion workbook's practical exercises in promoting critical thinking and deeper engagement.

True to the study of Pingil (2022), designing and developing learning materials can foster higher-order thinking skills through learners, timely and updated feedback, well-aligned objectives to activities, integrated skills, engaging texts, adaptable learning activities, and the use of scaffolding techniques. The research also emphasized that these attributes are very crucial in ensuring both the teacher and students to connect with the developed module's content, presentation, and style.

Clarity was **Highly Acceptable** (3.63). The indicator "Information is clear" had the highest mean of 3.93 while the indicator "Information suits learners' interest." had the lowest mean of 3.47 which was interpreted still as Highly Acceptable. The standard deviation was 0.40 that indicated moderate variation in the evaluators' responses.

The prior findings offer a compelling proof in favor that the companion workbook's clarity in terms of information is evidently considered by the research. The content is presented in a manner that is easy to understand, logically organized, and appropriate to the reading level of Grade 7.

This particular characteristic was supported by Fran (2022). The research had concluded that clarity of instruction's benefits can help the learners to enhance and to develop their higher-order thinking skills, independent learning, student participation, and creative thinking as clear materials could facilitate engagement that diverts from conventional thinking through a reduced cognitive load from unclear instructions.

Usefulness was **Highly Acceptable** (3.65). The indicator "The activities seek to relate new concepts from previous learnings" had the highest mean of 3.80 while the indicator "The material stimulates the learners to intellectual activities which help them master the Scholastic reading skills" had the lowest computed mean of 3.47 which was interpreted still as Highly Acceptable. The standard deviation was 0.24 that reflected low variation in the evaluators' responses.

The previous findings provide strong evidence that the usefulness of the companion workbook is effectively supporting both the reinforcement and application of reading concepts. The activities are designed to build on students' prior knowledge which make it easier for the students to connect new ideas with what they have already learned from the previous topics.

This particular integration of social-emotional learning skills and reading instruction enhances comprehension retention which contributes to a more meaningful learning experience. Although the stimulation of intellectual activities shows slightly lower ratings, it still reflects a solid capacity of the material to engage the students in critical thinking and skill mastery.

This developed companion workbook enhances the students' ability to connect their previous learnings to the new ideas presented to them which proves to be practical and purposeful learning resource in strengthening the Scholastic Reading Program. Furthermore, the standard deviation proves that interraters mostly agreed on the companion workbook's usefulness with only slight differences in how they perceived its

ability to stimulate thinking. A few may have rated it a bit lower because of their varying expectations and classroom experiences.

This was supported by Santos (as cited in Capistrano, 2024). According to the learning can help them to actively connect theoretical knowledge with practical applications which can enhance learners' ability to deepen comprehension. After all, learning is not only about absorption but is a process of knowledge construction which is connected to the study's main theory.

Presentation was **Highly Acceptable** (3.63). The indicator "Topics are presented in logical and sequential order" had the highest computed mean of 3.80 while the indicator "The direction is concise, readable, and easy to follow." had the lowest computed mean of 3.47 which was interpreted still as Highly Acceptable. The standard deviation was 0.42 that revealed moderate variation in the evaluators' responses.

The earlier findings strongly indicated that the companion workbook's topics are presented in a logical and sequential order. This implies that the companion workbook's organized layout helps both the teacher and students follow the lessons with ease. The logical flow of topics presented in the materials supports the students in understanding how each lesson connects to the next, promoting continuity and comprehension. The obtained standard deviation indicates a moderate level of variation which implies that while many interraters agree on the logical sequence of topics, others may have had slightly different views, possibly due to varying expectations on topic progression. Those interraters with more experience might have higher expectations for topic flow than novice ones. Additionally, some interraters are more familiar with the Scholastic Reading Program and the Umbrella Project might score more favorably while others might have missed the connection.

As stated by Araza and Magnaye (2023), a well-ordered, sequential, logically-presented topics can help the learners to grasp foundational and beginner's ideas before progressing to a more complex one. The study also mentioned that this particular characteristic of a well-developed workbook was aligned to the principles of an effective instructional design that believes that new idea can build upon the understanding gained from previous learned topics. This idea was closely related to another theory of this research which was the Zone of Proximal Development that emphasized the importance of scaffolding in learning.

Suitability was **Highly Acceptable** (3.56). The indicator "Activities consider the varying attitudes and capabilities of the learner" had the highest computed mean of 3.80 while the indicator "Language of the program is within the vocabulary range of the learners." had the lowest computed mean of 3.20 which was interpreted as Acceptable. The standard deviation was 0.32 that presented moderate variation in the evaluators' responses.

This means that the companion workbook appears to be thoughtfully designed to accommodate the diverse learning needs, readiness levels, and preferences of Grade 7 students which allows for more inclusive and responsive instruction. The activities likely promote engagement by offering content that students can relate and handle confidently. The reading level of each text helps the students to fully understand the reading concepts.

However, the standard deviation suggests a moderate level of variation. This implies to different factors such as difference in the interraters' teaching experiences, varying interpretations of what constitutes "inclusive" instruction, and slight disparities for students engagement.

The idea of matching the reading level of the learners and the text's readability level was supported by many studies. Tomas, Villaros, and Galman (2021) acknowledged that a mismatch between the text readability and students' comprehension level can hinder learners' academic performance. Their inability to read at their grade level may lead also to anxiety and depression which may destroy students' confidence to read.

Research Objective 3: Determine the pretest and posttest results of the Grade 7 students' reading comprehension level before and after implementing the developed and validated Companion Workbook.

There was a significant difference between the mean scores in the performance of the students in the pretest and posttest as the probability value was .000 which was less than the level of significance at .05. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.

It can be implied and concluded that the Companion Workbook Integrating Umbrella Project into Scholastic Reading Program for Grade 7 learners is effective, which evidently increases the learning acquisition of Grade 7 students based on the results in the pretest and posttest.

To support the mentioned the abovementioned results, research has suggested that integrating social-emotional learning skills into reading/literacy instruction can have a positive impact to the learners' reading performance. As stated by Laufenberg (2020), integrating social-emotional learning skills into reading texts was an effective strategy for enhancing reading comprehension. Activities like art, reflection, group discussions, writing activities, on-leveled texts, and graphic organizers can enhance students' connection to the selected texts. These activities were also incorporated in the companion workbook as reading activities that helped the learners better understand character's emotions, motivations, and actions in a story. Moreover, Anar and Barroso (2022) underscored the growing importance of interweaving cognitive, psychological, physical, and social-emotional factors in shaping the academic achievements of secondary school students in today's era.

The pretest result was **Very Satisfactory** (88.40). A significant majority of the class achieved an outstanding rating of 60.00 while a small number of the students fell under Fairly Satisfactory and did not meet expectations which has a percentage of 3.33.

This implies that the companion workbook, designed to integrate the Umbrella Project into the Scholastic Reading Program, is being introduced to a group of learners who already demonstrate a strong foundation in reading skills. The result also concludes that the companion workbook is likely reinforce and can enhance the students' existing competencies.

This was supported by Peffer (2023) that reading performance is closely linked to social-emotional well-being. Providing students with educational tools to manage emotions, clear behavioral expectations, and opportunities to build trust with peers and

adults fosters connections to school and community. This connection often leads to improved academic outcomes.

The posttest result was **Outstanding** (95.93). Majority of the class achieved an outstanding rating of 100.

This concludes that the companion workbook is effective in supporting and advancing students' reading competencies. The absence of any students in the lower performance categories also implies a high level of engagement, comprehension, and skill mastery across the entire group. Moreover, this reading growth success may reflect the quality of the companion workbook's indicators (Objectives, Directions, Topics, Practical Exercises, Clarity, Usefulness, Presentation, and Suitability) and the presence of a supportive learning environment. In conclusion, the change of the reading performance of the students is because of the alignment of the academic content to their social-emotional skills.

Elias (2023) mentioned that building strong social-emotional learning skills is crucial for enhancing reading comprehension through empathy, collaboration, and problem-solving skills. These social-emotional learning components not only strengthened the cognitive engagement with texts but also empowered the students to navigate reading challenges with resilience and confidence.

Additionally, in the study of Horan (2020), about the correlation between social-emotional skills and cognitive development, it has shown how children's adaptability to environmental changes is pivotal for their success in academics. The cultivation of social and emotional competencies, including empathy and self-regulation, plays a very powerful role in fostering cognitive growth among the students.

Conclusions

Upon the implementation of the two learning programs, The Scholastic Reading Program that used by the school to promote reading and enhance reading comprehension of the learners, and The Umbrella Project that promotes well-being by teaching the learners with necessary social-emotional learning skills, an educational need emerged for a resource that integrates these objectives into a developed companion workbook material has become the pivotal goal of this research.

This validated companion workbook was developed to bridge the gap by incorporating social-emotional skills into reading instructions. By aligning some selected Scholastic reading texts with different activities like art, reflection, group discussions, writing activities, on-leveled texts, and graphic organizers that were all infused with social-emotional skills, the research expected to help the learners be empowered in fostering academic success in terms of reading comprehension.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were offered:

1. The design of the companion workbook may intentionally embed social-emotional learning reflection prompts alongside reading comprehension activities so that

learners can connect texts with Umbrella Project skills. The findings shown that this integration not only strengthens literacy but also supports emotional growth, making the workbook a practical dual-purpose tool for teachers and students.

2. To ensure strong validity and acceptability, iterative validation cycles should involve both teacher-implementers and student feedback which allows the workbook to be refined for clarity, relevance, and engagement. The findings confirmed that expert validators rated the workbook highly valid and highly acceptable which supports its immediate classroom use. Schools may apply this by creating feedback loops where students and teachers co-evaluate instructional materials, ensuring learner-centered design.
3. The results revealed significant improvement in students' reading comprehension after using the workbook. To deepen application, schools can pair quantitative results with qualitative evidence such as student journals, reflections, or group discussions to capture growth in confidence, motivation, and comprehension strategies.
4. For the future researchers, they may replicate the study with larger cohorts, track longitudinal effects across multiple grade levels, and employ mixed-method designs to provide a richer understanding of how SEL integration sustains literacy gains over time. They may also explore digital workbook formats, and test scalability of SEL-Reading integration across different grade levels and school context.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was adhered to the ethical guidelines embedded in the institution's Research Manual. Consent was given to the respondents and a thorough explanation of the purpose and objectives of the study was also provided. Confidentiality of the data was strictly maintained throughout the data gathering. Proper citation and recognition of all authors' and researchers' works was duly observed in this study.

A consent letter was given to the respondents which explained the nature of the study and its significance to them. Furthermore, the research instruments were used in this research was only collected the relevant information about the variables included in the study and there were no private or personal questions asked to the respondents. The use of the Scholastic Reading Inventory and reading materials was also sought a permission from the Scholastic Philippines.

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